

The Office of the Tax Ombudsman and the Protection of the Rights of Tax Payers: An Appraisal

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Abstract:

The Parliament of Tanzania on 13th June 2019 passed the Finance Act 2019 which came into force on 1st July 2019. The Act amended the Tax Administration Act, Cap 438 of 2019, R.E. 2023, to establish an office known as the Tax Ombudsman Service. This Office is established within the Ministry of Finance and Planning. As an organ of state, it has a responsibility to uphold, defend, and advance the legal rights that taxpayers are granted. The Tax Ombudsman is endowed with only those powers and duties granted by law because it is a creation of statute. The Tax Ombudsman has shortcomings under the current tax laws that may undermine its ability to effectively protect the rights of taxpayers. These include the fact that the Tax Ombudsman Service office can only offer a decision made by the minister after submitting its findings and recommendations and that the powers and duties of the Tax Ombudsman are very limited. Since the office is still in its infancy, it is unclear how effective it is in defending rights; this will only become clear over time. However, more power of the kind suggested in this article must be granted to the Tax Ombudsman Service in order to secure its role as a custodian of rights.

Keywords: Tax Ombudsman Service, Tax Payers' Rights, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Establishing an independent government office that handles complaints about the tax administration's service delivery is becoming increasingly common in many jurisdictions around the world. It is necessary to have a mechanism to address taxpayer complaints of the violation of their rights and poor service delivery by the tax administrator. Traditional mechanisms, such as tribunals and courts, may not be effective, due to delays and the cost involved. As a result, the office of tax ombudsman has been established in many countries to safeguard taxpayers' rights and improve the overall tax system. This article therefore, appraises the role of the tax ombudsman in Tanzania. It begins with stating the problem, examining the concept of an ombudsman in general, and tax ombudsman in particular. The paper proceeds to highlight the establishment of the office of Tax Ombudsman in Tanzania, duties and functions of Tax Ombudsman, limitations of the powers of Tax Ombudsman, handling of complaints through tax ombudsman and conditions necessary for filling complaints.

In many countries, the office of Tax Ombudsman Service is established to protect the rights of tax payers. For these rights to be effectively realized, it is important to have a well-established mechanism which will be powerful enough to protect and deal with taxpayer's rights effectively. Regulation 7 of Tax Administration (Administration of Tax Ombudsman Service)¹ requires the Ombudsman to be independent and impartial in discharging his duties. Moreover, Regulation 10 (2) of the Tax Administration (Tax Ombudsman Service Complaint Procedure)² requires the Ombudsman within 14 days after determining the complaint, to submit his findings and recommendations to the minister, after which, the minister issues directives to the authority upon receipt of the findings. The decision of the minister is communicated to the complainant through the Ombudsman. This clearly shows that determination of taxpayers' rights depends on the decision of the minister, and this poses a question of independence and impartiality of the Tax Ombudsman in effective protection of tax payers' rights.

Furthermore, the powers and duties of the Ombudsman are limited. One of the limitations of the powers of the Ombudsman as stipulated under section 28 D of the Tax Administration Act is an objection decision. In cases where the Tax Revenue Authority (TRA) and the taxpayer are unable to come to an amicable agreement regarding the determination of the objection, the taxpayer's only option is to appeal, first to the Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB), then to the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal (TRAT), and finally to the Court of Appeal (CAT). In real life, this procedure can take five to ten years. Both the taxman and the taxpayer must deal with a significant administrative burden as a result. This poses the question of whether the Tax Ombudsman can expedite or fasten the dispute resolution process while his powers in relation to objection decision are limited.

¹ Tax Administration (Administration of Tax Ombudsman Service), GN No. 105 of 2022.

² Tax Administration (Tax Ombudsman Service Complaint Procedure) GN No. 106 of 2022.

This article therefore explores the effectiveness of the Tax Ombudsman in the discharge of its responsibilities. In addition, the paper examines the position of the laws and practice relating to the powers of the ombudsman in protecting the rights of Tanzanian taxpayers. The article relies on the analysis of statutory provisions, regulations, judicial decisions, and scholarly literature relating to the Tax Ombudsman, supplemented by socio-legal research methodologies. The combination of doctrinal and field-based approaches provides both theoretical and practical perspectives necessary for assessing the effectiveness of the Tax Ombudsman in protecting the rights of taxpayers in Tanzania.

1.1 Concept of Ombudsman

The Ombudsman is an independent government official who receives complaints against public agencies and officials, investigates the complaints, and makes recommendations to solve the complaints.³ In order to protect citizens' rights when dealing with the government, the Swedish Parliament established the Ombudsman position in 1809.⁴ This was the beginning of the modern ombudsman position.⁵ According to Hatchard,⁶ many other nations adopted the concept. In every country and province in the world, ombudsmen were established between 1966 and 1984. Tanzania (then Tanganyika) was the first African country to establish an ombudsman-type institution, when the Permanent Commission for Enquiry (PCE) was created in January 1964. Other African nations followed: Mauritius created a formal Ombudsman in 1970, and Zambia set up its Commission for Investigations in the 1973 Constitution, beginning operations in 1974. Uganda established the office of the Inspector General of Government by statute in 1986 (published in 1988), and later entrenched it as a constitutional body under the 1995 Constitution.⁷

2. ESTABLISHMENT OF THE OFFICE OF TAX OMBUDSMAN IN TANZANIA

The Tax Ombudsman Service is an independent body established under section 28A of the Tax Administration Act⁸ in order to protect the rights of tax payers against abuse of power by tax officers and ensure transparency and effective tax administration in Tanzania. In order to strengthen and protect tax payers' rights against potential abuse by tax officials, the Tanzanian Parliament amended the Tax Administration Act of 2015 in 2019 and created the Tax Ombudsman Service. The office is mandated to review and address any complaints by taxpayers regarding services, procedural or administrative

³ Rukundo, S. "Towards an Effective Taxpayer Complaint Handling Mechanism:" The Case for a Tax Ombudsman in Uganda, Working Paper 158, 2023, at P. 7.

⁴ Ferris, C., Goodman, B. and Mayer, G. Brief on the Office of the Ombudsman, prepared for presentation before the Ombudsman Committee at the International Bar Association Eighteenth Biennial Conference Occasional Paper 6, Berlin, 1980.

⁵ Buck et al, *The Ombudsman Enterprise and Administrative Justice*, Burlington, VT: Ashgate Publishers, 2011.

⁶ Hatchard, J. 'The Ombudsman in Africa Revisited', *The International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 1991, Pp. 937-948.

⁷ Bernard Frank, *The Tanzanian Permanent Commission of Inquiry - The Ombudsman*, 2 *Denv. J. Int'l L. & Pol'y* 255 (1972).

⁸ Cap. 438 [R.E 2019].

matters arising in the course of administering tax laws by the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), the Commissioner General or any staff of the TRA. The Tax Ombudsman Service is envisioned to be an impartial organization tasked with gathering accurate and unbiased information as well as complaints, primarily from taxpayers, regarding the Tanzania Revenue Authority's (TRA) handling of their tax affairs.

In addition to creating the Service, the amendments grant the Minister for Finance (the Minister) authority to make regulations that specify how the Service will conduct and handle complaints. The Tax Administration (Administration of Tax Ombudsman Service) Regulations,⁹ and the Tax Administration (Tax Ombudsman Service Complaint Procedure) Regulations,¹⁰ were released by the Minister on March 4, 2022, in the course of exercising these powers. According to the Tax Ombudsman Service Regulations, the Service must carry out its responsibilities independently and objectively, adhere to informal, equitable, and cost-effective procedures, be impartial, give consideration to equity-related issues, develop strategies for effectively resolving complaints, and maintain confidentiality. Any person may submit an oral or written complaint to the Service, either directly or through an authorized representative, if they are dissatisfied with the services provided by the Commissioner or any TRA staff.¹¹ Regarding the Service's authority to handle complaints, a person may file a claim against the TRA for failing to follow procedures or acting improperly, for failing to promptly release documents or assets that were seized, for failing to promptly address a taxpayer's complaint that the TRA received, or for failing to respond to letters or other documents sent to it.

2.1 Functions of the Tax Ombudsman

Section 28 C of the Tax Administration Act,¹² as amended by section 54 of the Finance Act,¹³ provides for the duties and functions of the Tax Ombudsman as follows; First, to review a complaint, and where necessary, resolve it amicably through mediation or conciliation, second, to act independently and impartially in handling complaints; third, to follow informal, fair and cost effective procedures in resolving complaints; fourth, to provide information, training and awareness to taxpayers on tax ombudsman service, functions and procedures of making complaints; fifth, to facilitate access by taxpayer to dispute resolution processes within the Authority; and lastly to identify and review tax administrative issues related to customer service, or procedures and behaviors which impact negatively on taxpayers.

2.2 Limitations of the powers of the Tax Ombudsman

Section 28 D of the Tax Administration Act as amended by the Finance Act,¹⁴ provides for the limitations as the Tax Ombudsman is unable to review the following; first, legislation or tax policy; second, Authority's policy or practice save that which relates to service,

⁹ GN No.105 of 2022.

¹⁰ GN No. 106 of 2022.

¹¹ Tarimo, N. & Mbowe, V. "The Ombudsman: The answer taxpayers have been waiting for?" Available at: <https://www.pwc.co.tz/press-room/the-ombudsman.html> (Accessed on 6/6/2023).

¹² Cap. 438 [R.E 2019].

¹³ Act No. 3 of 2021.

¹⁴ Act No. 3 of 2021.

administrative or procedural matter with respect to administration of tax laws; and third, tax decision or objection decision. Furthermore, any person employed by the Service is prohibited to hold any other office or employment where he or she will receive any salary.¹⁵

2.3 Handling and lodging of complaints through the Office of Tax Ombudsman Service

The Tax Ombudsman Service Complaint Procedure Regulations state that anyone may file a complaint regarding any of the following: non-compliance with procedures or improper administration by the TRA in administering tax laws; delay in the release of assets or documents seized during tax affairs investigations; delay in responding to a taxpayer's complaint; or non-response to letters or documents sent to the TRA.

Regulation 4(1) of the Tax Ombudsman Complaint Procedure Regulations¹⁶ permits any person to file a complaint with the Service if they are dissatisfied with the services provided by the Commissioner General or any TRA staff. A complaint may be submitted to the Tax Ombudsman Service verbally, in writing, electronically, in person, or through a duly authorized representative (Regulations 3 and 4(2) of the Tax Ombudsman Complaint Procedure Regulations).¹⁷

Regarding the Tax Ombudsman Service's authority to handle complaints, Regulation 5 of the Tax Ombudsman Complaint Procedure Regulations states that anyone may file a grievance regarding TRA's non-compliance with procedures or improper administration, delay in releasing records or property seized during an investigation of tax matters, delay in responding to a taxpayer's complaint filed with TRA, and non-response to letters or documents sent. Any complaint to the Tax Ombudsman Service must be filed in a prescribed form as specified in the Complaint Procedure Regulations within 90 days of the occurrence of the disputed event. The complaint form must be accompanied by a declaration that the complainant has used every internal complaint procedure offered by TRA, as well as copies of any correspondence the complainant has had with the latter organization, as well as any other pertinent documents or information.

2.4 Conditions for filing complaints

In order for the Tax Ombudsman Service to consider a complaint, the complainant's written representation to the TRA must have been rejected, the TRA must have failed to respond within 30 days, or the complainant must not have been satisfied with the TRA's response before the complaint was submitted. Additionally, unless there is new information that is likely to influence the outcome, the Tax Ombudsman Service will not consider a complaint regarding a matter that has already been resolved in a prior complaint.¹⁸

¹⁵ Regulation 6 of GN No.106.

¹⁶ GN No. 105/106 of 2022.

¹⁷ GN No. 105/106 of 2022.

¹⁸ Regulation 7 (3) of GN No. 106 of 2022.

2.5 Determination of complaints

The Tax Ombudsman Service must resolve the issue after receiving a complaint within 30 days of the date of receipt.¹⁹ The Tax Ombudsman Service may handle the conflict through mediation, conciliation, or any other peaceful dispute resolution technique that the Service deems appropriate. Additionally, the Service has the right to reject the complaint, ignore it, or uphold it in whole or in part.²⁰ According to Rukundo, the following criteria should be checked when determining complaints: whether they were submitted within the allotted time period; whether they fall under the purview of the office; whether the Ombudsman office has been given a chance to respond; whether going to court would provide a more effective remedy; whether there is prima facie evidence that the complaint is justified; and whether the complainant has possibly suffered an injustice. In order to take control of a complaint after it has been filed without further input from the complainant, the ombudsman should rely on investigative techniques.²¹

In practice, a large number of complaints to the office of Ombudsman are from individuals, and the vast majority lodged complaints without any representation. Many of those represented were represented by family members or friends.²² Second, the Tax Ombudsman office is not generally known to the taxpayers and the public at large. Many taxpayers are not aware of the existence of the Tax Ombudsman Office.²³ The Tax Appeals Boards and Tax Appeals Tribunal, as well as the Court of Appeal of Tanzania, have been for a long time seen to be the only solutions to taxpayers' complaints.

Third, the powers of the Tax Ombudsman remain very limited and do not adequately cover the full spectrum of taxpayers' rights and needs. The existing legal framework under the Tax Administration Act restricts the Ombudsman's jurisdiction, particularly by excluding disputes arising from objection decisions, which are instead directed to the Tax Revenue Appeals Board and the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal. This limitation significantly constrains the Ombudsman's capacity to offer effective remedies to taxpayers and undermines its intended role as an independent protector of taxpayers' rights. Fourth, the decision of the Tax Ombudsman is binding; however, such decision is from the Minister who oversees the office of the Tax Ombudsman. The study reveals that the office is still not so effective since it only handles complaints of the taxpayers and submit its findings and recommendations to the minister for a decision. The Office only communicate such decision to the parties which makes it to be less effective and not impartial in protecting taxpayers' rights contrary to the principles of the Tax Ombudsman

¹⁹ Regulation 10 (1) of GN No. 106 of 2022.

²⁰ Regulation 9 (1) of GN No. 106 of 2022.

²¹ Rukundo, S. "Towards an Effective Taxpayer Complaint Handling Mechanism:" The Case for a Tax Ombudsman in Uganda, Working Paper 158, 2023, at P. 7 P. 33.

²² The interview conducted by the researcher with two officers from the Office of the Tax Ombudsman at the Ministry of Finance and Planning Headquarters, Dodoma, on 15 April 2025 at 10:00 a.m. The interview was part of the field data collection process for this study and focused on the types of complaints received and the level of taxpayer representation.

²³ Information obtained from an experienced advocate of the High Court of Tanzania from Chimba Attorneys located Mnazi Mmoja Dar es salaam on 4th June 2025.

who is required by law to be independent, impartial and objective. Therefore, it is the researcher's view that taxpayers' rights will not effectively being protected by the Tax Ombudsman office unless the Tax Ombudsman is vested by law with more powers to cover situations where cases are submitted to the Tax Revenue Authority Board and Tax Revenue Authority Tribunal and to the Court of Appeal. Taxpayers' rights will also be effectively protected when the office gets absolute power to make decisions and is not dependent on the Minister responsible, since the office is an independent institution.

3. SECURING THE INDEPENDENCE OF THE TAX OMBUDSMAN

The effectiveness of the Tax Ombudsman is directly linked to its independence, both institutional and operational. Although Regulation 7²⁴ emphasizes independence and impartiality, the current framework places the office within the Ministry of Finance and Planning, creating potential conflicts of interest. Since the Minister also issues the final decision on the Ombudsman's recommendations, the office's autonomy is significantly curtailed. To secure true independence, the office should be restructured as an autonomous statutory agency reporting to Parliament rather than the executive. This is the position of the Insurance Ombudsman Regulations,²⁵ where the Minister appoints the Ombudsman, who operates independently of the Tanzania Insurance Regulatory Authority (TIRA). Parliament could establish a Tax Ombudsman Board to oversee appointments, budget, and operations, ensuring separation from the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) and the Ministry of Finance. Judicial precedents such as *National Insurance Corporation v Insurance Ombudsman*²⁶ underscore the principle that the Ombudsman's independence must be preserved to maintain public confidence and administrative fairness.

4. ACHIEVEMENTS AND CHALLENGES OF THE TAX OMBUDSMAN

Since its establishment in 2019, the Office of the Tax Ombudsman has made incremental progress. It has created an alternative platform for taxpayers to lodge service-related complaints against the TRA, promoting accountability and procedural fairness.²⁷ Ombudsman staff revealed that informal mediation and advisory interventions have resolved minor administrative complaints without resorting to litigation. Additionally, the office has contributed to a gradual shift in taxpayer perception, encouraging non-confrontational dialogue between taxpayers and tax officials. Despite notable progress, the Tax Ombudsman continues to face significant obstacles that undermine its effectiveness. The office lacks true independence due to ministerial control over final decisions, while its jurisdiction remains narrowly confined, excluding objection matters and disputes before the Tax Appeals Board or Tribunal. Public awareness of the office's role is still low, compounded by limited financial and human resources that restrict its outreach and operational efficiency.

²⁴ Tax Administration (Administration of Tax Ombudsman Service) Regulations, 2022

²⁵ Ombudsman Insurance Regulations, GN 411of 2013.

²⁶ (Commercial Case No. 13 of 2012, HCT–Commercial Division, TanzLII).

²⁷ Kalage, A. (2020). Administrative Justice and the Role of Ombudsmen in Tanzania. *Journal of African Law*, 64(2), 215–234.

Moreover, the Ombudsman's recommendations are merely advisory, lacking binding force. To address these shortcomings, legislative amendments to Section 28D of the Tax Administration Act²⁸ should expand its mandate to include systemic maladministration and objection-related issues, while granting limited binding authority to its recommendations, subject to lawful review. Ensuring an independent budget, enhancing public education through media and seminars, and requiring annual reports to Parliament would further strengthen its transparency, autonomy, and impact in protecting taxpayers' rights.

5. RELATIONSHIP WITH THE TAX APPEALS BOARD AND TAX REVENUE APPEALS TRIBUNAL

The Tax Ombudsman, the Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB), and the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal (TRAT) share complementary although sometimes overlapping functions in tax dispute resolution. TRAB and TRAT adjudicate disputes arising from tax assessments and objection decisions under the Tax Revenue Appeals Act, while the Tax Ombudsman addresses service delivery and administrative complaints.²⁹ However, the overlap arises when taxpayers perceive administrative unfairness in the process of assessment or objection handling, which also underpins appeals before TRAB or TRAT. To avoid duplication, the law should clearly delineate the Ombudsman's jurisdiction to service and procedural matters only, excluding substantive tax determinations. Coordination mechanisms, such as a Memorandum of Understanding between the Ombudsman and the TRAB/TRAT, could ensure mutual referral of complaints and promote coherent dispute management. Judicial guidance from *Golden Key Insurance Ltd v Commissioner of Insurance and Another*³⁰ illustrates that while Ombudsmen should not usurp the adjudicatory role of tribunals, they serve a vital complementary function in administrative justice.

5.1 Why maintain the Ombudsman despite the existence of TRAB and TRAT?

The existence of the Ombudsman is justified even with the Tax Appeals Board and Tribunal in place because its role is preventive, remedial, and facilitative rather than adjudicatory. Courts and tribunals are often adversarial, time-consuming, and costly. The Ombudsman, conversely, promotes early resolution through mediation and conciliation, core principles of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR). Moreover, the Ombudsman's intervention can address systemic administrative weaknesses such as delays, non-responsiveness, or poor service culture that tribunals cannot easily remedy. This aligns with the objective of administrative justice and the constitutional principle of good governance under Article 8 of the Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania (1977).

6. PUBLIC AWARENESS AND ACCESS TO THE TAX OMBUDSMAN

Public awareness of the Tax Ombudsman remains very low, as most taxpayers are unfamiliar with its existence, functions, and complaint procedures. To address this, a structured and continuous public awareness program should be institutionalized to

²⁸ As Revised by section 29 of TAA R.E 2023 Cap 438.

²⁹ Msuya, E. (2021). "Enhancing Taxpayer Rights through Alternative Dispute Resolution: The Tanzanian Perspective." *Eastern Africa Law Review*, Vol. 48.

³⁰ (Commercial Case No. 21 of 2016, HCT–Commercial Division, TanzLII

educate taxpayers about their rights and the mechanisms available for redress.³¹ Drawing lessons from the Insurance Ombudsman's outreach model, the Tax Ombudsman should publish annual reports and accessible summaries of resolved cases to demonstrate transparency and accountability. Regular workshops and stakeholder dialogues with business associations, professional bodies, and civil society organizations would further disseminate information and build confidence in the office's role. Establishing a user-friendly website, active social media platforms, and a toll-free helpline would improve accessibility, particularly for small and medium taxpayers who may lack direct contact with TRA offices.³² Additionally, the Tanzania Revenue Authority should collaborate with the Ombudsman to display its contact details and complaint procedures on tax forms, assessment notices, and other correspondence. These strategies would enhance the visibility and credibility of the Ombudsman, foster voluntary tax compliance, and promote a culture of trust and fairness in tax administration.

7. LESSONS FROM THE INSURANCE OMBUDSMAN IN TANZANIA

The experience of the Insurance Ombudsman in Tanzania provides valuable insights for strengthening the Tax Ombudsman. Established under the Insurance Act,³³ and the Insurance Ombudsman Regulations, 2009, the office demonstrates a higher degree of institutional independence and procedural effectiveness. Judicial recognition in cases such as *National Insurance Corporation v Insurance Ombudsman*³⁴ affirms its quasi-judicial authority and reinforces its credibility in resolving disputes. The Insurance Ombudsman's success is primarily attributed to its clear procedural framework that guarantees fairness and finality in complaint handling, its consistent publication of annual reports to the Tanzania Insurance Regulatory Authority (TIRA) and the public to ensure transparency, and the persuasive weight of its determinations, which, though not legally binding, are generally respected and implemented.³⁵ By adopting similar measures ensuring procedural autonomy, accountability, and the practical enforceability of recommendations, the Tax Ombudsman can evolve into a more effective, trusted, and resilient institution for protecting taxpayers' rights.

8. CONCLUSION

The relationship between the taxpayer and the tax authority is inherently tense in Tanzania. This situation is aggravated by poor service delivery from the TRA and the inefficiency of the laws. The tax ombudsman is therefore a suitable remedy to this challenge when given more power to deal with the said disputes. Professor Fernando Serrano, the tax ombudsman for the municipality of Madrid in Spain once said, "The creation of a Tax Ombudsman has two effects: first, it supplements the civic instruments

³¹ Mkwazu Ziada O. (2024) Legal Challenges Facing the Tax Ombudsman Services Office in Resolving Dispute in Mainland Tanzania. *International Journal of Law Management & Humanities* <https://doi.org/10.10000/IJLMH.118390>. Accessed in October 2025.

³² Examining public awareness of the Office of the Tax Ombudsman in South Africa. *Journal of Public Administration*, 57(2): 331-343.

³³ Cap. 394.

³⁴ [2012] HCT-Commercial Division.

³⁵ Kalage, A. (2020). Administrative Justice and the Role of Ombudsmen in Tanzania. *Journal of African Law*, 64(2), 215-234.

for dialogue and defence that should be available to all taxpayers; and secondly, in the medium term, the Tax Ombudsman's action has positive and valuable effects on the smooth functioning and quality of services provided by the Tax Administration".³⁶

³⁶ Serrano, F. *The Taxpayer's Rights and the Role of the Tax Ombudsman: 'an Analysis from a Spanish and Comparative Law Perspective'*, Intertax, 2007, Pp. 331-340.